

Nanotechnology

Paper Id : 20942 Submission Date : 2025-12-01 Acceptance Date : 2025-12-22 Publication Date : 2025-12-25

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.18231467

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/innovation.php#8>

Sandeep Kumar

Assistant Professor
Department Of Physics
J.V. Jain College
Saharanpur,U.P., India

Vakul Bansal

Principal
J.V. Jain College
Saharanpur, U.P., India

Abstract

Nanotechnology is the science of functional systems at the molecular scale. This covers both current work and concepts in more advanced form. Nanotechnology refers to the projected ability to construct items from the bottom up, using techniques being developed today to make complete, high-performance products.

One nanometer (nm) is 10^{-9} , of a meter. On comparison, the spacing between these atoms in a molecule of the order of 0.12-0.15 nm, and a DNA double helix has a radius of around 1 nm. or we can say the smallest cellular life-forms, the bacteria of the genus Mycoplasma are around 200 nm along length. or we can say nanotechnology is taken as the scale range 1 to 100 nm following the definition used by the National Nanotechnology Initiative in the US. The upper limit is more or less arbitrary but is around the size below which the phenomena not observed in larger structures start to become apparent and can be made use of in the nano device. These new phenomena make nanotechnology distinct from devices which are merely miniaturised versions of an equivalent macroscopic device; such devices are on a larger scale and come under the description of micro technology.

Keywords

Nanotechnology, Nanoscale.

Introduction

The prefix nano in the word nanotechnology means a billionth (1×10^{-9}) It deals with the various structures of matter having dimension of the order of 10^{-9} of a mete. While the word nanotechnology is relatively new, the existence, of functional devices, and structures of nanometer dimensions is not new, and in fact such structures have existed on Earth as long as life itself. The abalone, a mollusc, constructs very strong shells having indecent inner surfaces by organizing calcium carbonate into strong nanostructure bricks held together by a glue made of a carbohydrate-protein mix. Cracks initiated on the outside are unable to move through the shell because of the nanostructure bricks. The shell represent a natural demonstration that a structure fabricated from nanoparticle can be much stronger.

Objective of study

The study is to explain the concept, scale, and scientific foundations of nanotechnology as applied to functional systems at the molecular and atomic levels. This study is to examine the difference between nanotechnology and conventional micro-scale technologies with reference to size- dependent phenomena. To analyze the applications of nanotechnology in medical field such as drug delivery, diagnostics, surgery, and medical robotics. Along with the role of nanotechnology in electronics, to minimize the power efficiency, and enhancement of device performance.

This study is to assess the advantages of nanotechnology in terms of material strength, durability, cost efficiency and industrial productivity. It is to investigate the health, safety, and environment concerns associated with nanoparticles and nanomaterials. To identify the social impacts of nanotechnology, such as employment shifts as well as changes in manufacturing practices and to highlight the potential risks of misuse of nanotechnology in the field of environmental pollution.

Review of Literature

The literature of review is an our view of the already work published on the topic nanotechnology. This term can refer to a full research paper or a section of a scholarly work such a book of nanotechnology or any article. In either way it supposed to provide the researcher and audience with the general image of the existing wide knowledge of nanotechnology under questions for a better literature review we ensure that proper research methodology has been chosen. To be precise, the literature serves to situate the current study of the body and it provides context to the readers. In such cases review is present before methodology and result of the work.

Analysis**Impactions****Health and environmental concerns**

A video on the health and safety implications of nanotechnology Main articles; health and safety hazards of nanomaterials and Pollution from nanomaterials.

Nanofibers are used in several areas and in different products, in everything from aircraft wings to tennis rackets. Inhaling airborne nanoparticles and nanofibers may lead to a number of pulmonary diseases, e.g. fibrosis. Researchers it is found that when rats breathed in nanoparticles, the particles settled in the brain and lungs, which result significant increases in biomarkers and that nanoparticles induce skin aging through oxidative stress in hairless mice.

A Nature Nanotechnology study suggests some forms of carbon nanotubes a poster child for the "nanotechnology revolution"- could be as harmful as asbestos if inhaled in sufficient quantities. Anthony Seaton of the Institute of Occupational Medicine in Edinburgh, Scotland, who contributed to the article on carbon nanotubes said "We know that some of them probably have the potential to cause mesothelioma. So those sorts of materials needs to be handled very carefully." In the absence of specific regulation forthcoming from governments, Paull an Lyons (2008) have called for an exclusion of engineered nanoparticles in food. A newspaper article reports that workers in a paint factory developed serious lung disease and nanoparticles were found in their lungs.

Nanotechnology in Medicine

Application of Medical Nanotechnology span across a variety of areas such as.

1. In Drugs, Medicines etc
2. In diagnostic of diseased, abnormal conditionsl Etc.
3. In Surgery
4. In Medical Robotics
5. In the general sake of increasing knowledge of the Human Body.

Nanotechnology in Electronics

1. Application of Nanotechnology in electronics improves the capabilities of electronic devices. Moreover, it decreases their weight and power consumption. It improves the density of memory chips. It also reduces the size of transistors used in integrated circuits (IC).
2. Generally, Nanometer scale refers to the electronic circuits < 100nm.
3. $1\text{nm}=10^{-9}\text{m}$

Advantages of Nanotechnology

1. With nanotechnology we can create Unique materials and product which are stronger lighter cheaper, durable and precise.
2. Industrial computer which made with nanomaterial can become of billion time faster and million time smaller.
3. Automatic population clean up.
4. Manufacturing at very low cost or no cost.
5. In medical field-end of illness (that is cancer and heart disease)
6. universal immunity such disease like flu.
7. Less pollution
8. Mass production in food and consumable.

Disadvantages of nanotechnology

1. Health and safety issue, Nanoparticles can cause Serious
2. illness or damage of human body. Carbon Nanotubes can cause Infection of lungs.
3. Loss of job in manufacturing And farming etc.
4. Atomic weapons could be More assessable and destructive
5. Nano pollution is created by Toxic waste.

Conclusion

Nanotechnology holds immense promise to transform human life. Its significance lies in its vast potential to bring groundbreaking advancements across nearly all sectors, including medicine, computer technology, environmental cleanup. and the development of enerty sources.

Although nanotechnology offers various advantages, it is still at an early stage of development, with only a limited number of applications currently commercialized. Many innovations have yet to undergo complete life-cycle evaluations. While the pace of technological advancement in nanotechnology is accelerating, research into its possible environment has not progressed at the same rate.

As societies increasingly embrace this emerging technological revolution, equal emphasis must be placed on understanding its potential risks and impacts. Such efforts are crucial to prevent nanomaterials from becoming a major hazard of the 21st century. Ultimately, the long-term sustainability of nanotechnology will depend on the proper identification and management of its associated risks.

References

1. Drexler, K. Eric (1986). *Engines of Creation: The coming Era of Nanotechnology*. Doubleday. ISBN 9780385199735. OCLC 12752328.
2. *Jump up to:*^{-ab} Drexler, K. Eric (1992). *Nanosystems: Molecular machinery, manufacturing and Computations*, New York: John Wiley & Sons. ISBN 9780471575474, ICLC 26503231.
3. Hubber, A. (2010). "Digital quantum batteries: Energy and information storage in nanovacuum tube arrays". *Complexity*. 15(5):48-55. doi:10.1002/cplx.20306. S2CID 6994736.
4. Shinn. E. (2012). "Nuclear energy conversion with stacks of grapheme nanocapacitors". *Complexity*. 18 (3) : 24- 27. Bibcode: 2013 Cmplx. 18c. 24S. doi: 10.1002/cplx:21427. S2CID 35742708.
5. Elishkoff, I.D. Pentaras, K. Dujat,. C. Versaci. g. Muscolino, J. Stroch, S. Bucas, N. Challamel, T. Natsuki, Y.Y. Zhang. C.M. Wang and g. Ghyselinck, *Carbon Nanotubes and nano Sensors: Vibrations, Buckling, and ballistic Impact*, ISTE-Wiley, London, 2012, XIII+pp.421; ISBN 978-1- 84821-345-6.
6. Lyon, David; et. al. (2013). "Gap size dependence of the dielectric strength in nano vacuum gaps." *Gap size dependence of the Dielectrics and Electrical Insulation*. 20(4): 1467-1471. doi: 10.1109/TDEI.2013.6571470, S2CID 709782.
7. Saini, Rajiv; Saini, Santosh; Sharma, Sugandha (2010). "nanotechnology: The Future Medicine". *Journal of Cutaneous and Aesthetic Surgery*. 3 (1):32-33. doi: 10.4103/0974-2077.63301.PMC 2890134. PMID 20606992.
8. Belkin, A. et. al. (2015). "Self Assembled Wiggling Nano-Structures and the Principle of Maximum entropy Production". *Sci. Rep.* 5: 8323. Bibcode: 2015 Nat Sr..... 5E8323B. doi: 10.1038/srep08323,PMC 4321171. PMID 25662746.